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Geographical distribution of potential mechanical vectors implicated in Surra transmission in Spain: an entomological perspective

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Abstract

Background Haematophagous Diptera can transmit a wide range of diseases to both humans and animals. Some species of the *Trypanosoma* genus rely on these vectors for transmission, either cyclically or mechanically. *Trypanosoma evansi*, the causative agent of Surra, is the only African-origin trypanosome species detected in Spain to date, which is mechanically transmitted.

Methods To assess the occurrence and distribution of potential mechanical vectors at the national level, a systematic review was conducted on the Hippoboscidae, Muscidae and Tabanidae families. The review followed the methodology established by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and adhered to PRISMA guidelines. Data were compiled from 43 peer-reviewed scientific publications and four citizen science digital databases.

Results The review identified three genera belonging to the Hippoboscidae, two of the Muscidae and ten of the Tabanidae families. Genus-level distribution maps were generated for each group.

Conclusions This atlas serves as a valuable tool for the prevention and control of vector-borne animal trypanosomiasis in Spain. Nonetheless, further studies on the distribution, ecology and behaviour of haematophagous dipterans are essential to better understand their role in disease transmission and their potential impact on future outbreaks.

Keywords Diptera, Surra, Maps, Muscidae, Hippoboscidae, Tabanidae, Citizen science databases, Atlas

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Background

Haematophagous arthropods play a critical role in both human and animal health [69]. Their blood-feeding behaviour can cause direct harm, including irritation, immune reactions and localised trauma. Indirectly, they act as vectors for a wide range of infectious agents, facilitating both mechanical and biological (i.e. cyclical) transmission [87]. Among these pathogens, protozoans of the genus *Trypanosoma* (Gruby, 1843; Kinetoplastida: Trypanosomatidae) are of particular concern owing to their impact on veterinary and human medicine.

Animal trypanosomiasis, transmitted by vectors and manifesting as either Nagana and Surra, poses a significant barrier to livestock production across many African regions. Nagana is caused by *Trypanosoma brucei* (Plimmer & Bradford, 1899), *Trypanosoma vivax* (Ziemann, 1905) and *Trypanosoma congolense* (Brodin, 1904), while *Trypanosoma evansi* (Chauvrat, 1896) causes Surra [17]. Unlike other trypanosomes, *T. evansi* does not need a biological vector and is instead transmitted mechanically by haematophagous insects [18, 72]. However, the parasite's limited survival time within the insect's mouthparts constrains transmission efficiency.

Haematophagous dipterans are the most relevant vectors of *T. evansi*, owing to their high mobility and frequent feeding patterns [18, 67, 87]. Several studies highlighted the role of different insect taxa in the transmission of Surra to mammals, including biting flies of the tribe Stomoxyini (Diptera: Muscidae) (*Stomoxys* spp. and *Haematobia* spp.), tabanids (Diptera: Tabanidae) (*Tabanus* spp., *Atylotus* spp. and *Chrysops* spp., among others) and louse flies (Diptera: Hippoboscidae) (*Hippobosca* spp., *Lipoptena* spp. and *Melophagus* spp.) [20].

Surra is mainly found in North Africa, Northeast Africa, Latin America, the Middle East and Asia. However, outbreaks have also been reported in Europe, including France (Aveyron Department) and Spain. In the latter country, cases were recorded in the province of Alicante (mainland Spain), linked to the movement of infected animals from the Canary Islands [15, 82]. The first confirmed case of Surra in Spain occurred in 1997 on the Island of Gran Canaria [46], which led to subsequent studies to assess the parasite's prevalence in dromedaries and other livestock, as well as the potential role of rodents and haematophagous insects in disease maintenance [60, 73–75].

Although no new seropositive cases of Surra have been reported in the Canary Islands since 2022 [57, 83], ongoing surveillance and research into disease dynamics remain essential to prevent future outbreaks. This is particularly relevant, as Spain may act as an entry point for the disease into mainland Europe. In this context, the current study aims to compile a comprehensive atlas

of the distribution of potential *T. evansi* vectors across Spain, within the framework of the COMBAT project (COntrolling and progressively Minimizing the Burden of Animal Trypanosomiasis) [8]. This work complements the recently published national atlas of Surra in the country [57].

Methods

Search protocol and selection criteria

A systematic review was carried out in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [59], and following the methodology established by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) for continental and national atlases of *Glossina* spp. and African trypanosomes [1, 11–14, 21, 42, 65, 71, 80]. In addition, scientific repositories and search engines, including PubMed®, Scopus, Google Scholar and ResearchGate were used, without date restrictions. The collection and analysis period of the data from these platforms extended from February to December 2024.

The review focused on insect taxa identified as potential mechanical vectors of *T. evansi*, with particular attention on the families Muscidae, Hippoboscidae and Tabanidae [15, 17–19, 56, 75, 82]. Genera within each family were selected on the basis of prior literature, including *Stomoxys* and *Haematobia* for Muscidae [17, 18], and mammophilic genera for Hippoboscidae (*Hippobosca*, *Lipoptena*, and *Melophagus*) [84]. For the Tabanidae, the classification followed the nomenclature proposed by Portillo (2002) for horsefly in Spain, encompassing *Atylotus*, *Chrysops*, *Dasyrhamphis*, *Haematopota*, *Hybomitra*, *Nemorius*, *Pangonius*, *Philipomyia*, *Silvius*, and *Tabanus*.

Keyword searches were conducted in Spanish, French and English, using terms such as 'Diptera', 'Spain', 'Canary Islands', 'Balearic Islands', 'mainland Spain', 'Haematophagous', 'Muscidae', 'Hippoboscidae', 'Tabanidae', '*Stomoxys*', '*Stomoxys*', '*Haematobia*', '*Lipoptena*', '*Hippobosca*', '*Melophagus*', '*Tabanus*', '*Haematopota*', '*Dasyrhamphis*', '*Atylotus*', '*Pangonius*', '*Silvius*', '*Chrysops*', '*Hybomitra*', '*Nemorius*', '*Philipomyia*', '*Trypanosoma evansi*' and 'Surra'. Approximately less than 10% of the studies identified were excluded owing to access restrictions, often related to publication age or paywalls. However, some were retained indirectly through citations in other included sources.

Citizen science platforms

Data from citizen science platforms were obtained from four sources: iNaturalist (Nugent, 2018), GBIF.org, Biodiversidad Virtual (<https://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org>) and the Biodiversity Data Bank of the Canary Islands

(BDBC) (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota>). Searches were conducted using insect genera or species keywords, and results were filtered by country (last accessed: 11 March 2025). These platforms primarily provide presence-only records, often accompanied by precise geographical coordinates, occurrence dates and photographic evidence.

Only records validated by experts were retained. When expert validation was unavailable, all submitted images were manually reviewed. Duplicate entries across platforms were cross-checked and excluded.

Digital repository and database

The literature retrieved through the systematic review was compiled in a digital repository, and the following information were extracted regarding the occurrence of target insect taxa:

- **Sources:** Full reference details of each document, including authors, title, date and journal.
- **Site geographical data (Geo_Data_Site):** Sampling locations reported in the documents, georeferenced using Google Earth or Spanish National Geographic System when not explicitly stated. Location accuracy varied, from specific coordinates to approximate central points of municipalities. For broad designations (e.g., nature reserves), the centroid of the defined area was used.
- **Site entomological data (Entomo_Data_Site):** Descriptions of insect findings at each site, including collection date, taxonomic identification (family, genus, species, subspecies), number of individuals, trap types and survey duration.
- **Trap geographical data (Geo_Data_Trap):** Exact coordinates of sampling sites when such detail was available in the source publications.
- **Trap entomological data (Entomo_Data_Trap):** Entomological data associated with specific trap sites, mirroring the structure of *Entomo_Data_Site* but with finer spatial resolution.

Mapping

Genus-level occurrence maps for each insect family were generated using QGIS Geographic Information System (version 3.34.11, QGIS Association). The data presented on these maps were separated into two categories: literature-based records and citizen science records. To harmonise spatial reporting, particularly for entries derived from broader administrative units, the number of genera recorded per province was also indicated on the maps.

Results

This study analysed 105 species across 15 genera and three families, on the basis of a total of 2709 data records published between 1951 and 2024 throughout Spain. From the literature, 43 sources were consulted (40 scientific publications, two books and one doctoral thesis) (see Additional file 1: text S1 for more information), yielding 1088 presence records. From citizen science platforms, 1621 presence records were included. Although GBIF.org aggregates records from iNaturalist and Biodiversidad Virtual, 65% originated from Biodiversidad Virtual, 20% from iNaturalist and 15% from GBIF. Biodiversity Data Bank of the Canary Islands (BDBC) records were limited to the Canary Islands and lacked specific coordinates.

A total of 323 locations were georeferenced from the literature: 23 at the trap level or exact capture site, and 300 at broader spatial resolutions. In contrast, 90% of citizen science records were georeferenced with precise coordinates.

Some literature sources included quantitative trapping data. The total number of captured or observed insects during the study period was 20,076 individuals. Of the 1088 literature-based records, 18,455 insects were quantified: 86.5% belonged to the Muscidae family, 13.3% to the Tabanidae family and 0.2% to the Hippoboscidae. Each citizen science record was assumed to represent a single observed individual, totalling 1621 insects, of which 64.8% were Tabanidae, 19.2% Muscidae and 16% Hippoboscidae.

Table 1 summarises the families and genera included in the study, indicating the number of species per genus, number of provinces in which each genus was recorded, host species and trapping methods cited in the literature. Species-level details can be found in Additional file 2: Table S1.

Hippoboscidae family

Three mammophilic genera were reviewed within the Hippoboscidae family (Fig. 1). The *Hippobosca* genus showed the highest number of observations, primarily in northern, north-eastern, central and central-eastern and southern mainland Spain, with additional sightings in both Canary Islands provinces, and in the Balearic Islands.

The *Lipoptena* genus was mostly observed in the northern, north-eastern and south-western mainland Spain, with no records from the Canary or the Balearic islands.

Finally, the *Melophagus* genus was represented by a few isolated in northern, central and central-western mainland Spain, as well as the western Canary Islands.

Table 1 Summary of the blood-feeding dipteran families analysed in Spain (from 1951 to 2024). *N*: number; ND: not described

Family	Genus	Species (<i>N</i>)	Provinces (<i>N</i>)	Cited hosts	Cited capture methods
Hippoboscidae	<i>Hippobosca</i> Linnaeus, 1758	2	44	Equids, bovids, canids, felids, human	Trap (Sticky), sweep
	<i>Lipoptena</i> Nitzsch, 1818	3	16	Cervids, human	Trap (Suction)
	<i>Melophagus</i> Latreille, 1802	1	6	<i>Ovis aries</i> , cervids	ND
Muscidae	<i>Stomoxys</i> Geoffroy, 1762	1	44	Equids, ruminants, camelids, human	Trap (Sticky, suction, BG-sentinel, Nzi), sweep
	<i>Haematobia</i> Lepeletier & Serville, 1828	2	14	Bovids, human	Trap (Sticky, suction, CDC-Miniature light trap)
Tabanidae	<i>Atylotus</i> Osten-Sacken, 1876	9	20	Equids, bovids	Trap (Canopy, Malaise), sweep
	<i>Chrysops</i> Meigen, 1803	7	40	Equids, bovids, cervids	Trap (Canopy, Malaise), sweep
	<i>Dasyrhamphis</i> Enderlein, 1922	3	25	Equids	Sweep
	<i>Haematopota</i> Meigen, 1803	12	38	Equids, bovids	Trap (Canopy, Malaise), sweep
	<i>Hybomitra</i> Enderlein, 1922	12	23	Equids, bovids	Trap (Malaise, H-trap), sweep
	<i>Nemorius</i> Rondani, 1856	1	3	Equids, bovids	ND
	<i>Pangonius</i> Latreille, 1802	14	30	Equids, human	Sweep
	<i>Philipomyia</i> Olsufjev, 1964	2	21	Equids, bovids	Trap (Canopy, Malaise), sweep
	<i>Silvius</i> Meigen, 1820	3	8	Equids, bovids	Trap (Malaise)
	<i>Tabanus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	33	44	Equids, bovids, human	Trap (Canopy, Malaise, Sticky, H-trap), sweep

Fig. 1 Geographic distribution of Hippoboscidae family in Spain (1951–2024). The map includes mainland Spain (centre), the Balearic Islands (right) and the Canary Islands (bottom left)

Muscidae family

Two genera were reviewed within the Muscidae family (Fig. 2). Sightings of the *Stomoxys* genus were distributed across most of Spain, especially in the northern, southern and central regions of mainland regions. In addition, all islands of the Balearic and Canary archipelagos reported sightings. Observations of the genus *Haematobia* were concentrated in the northern, central and southern mainland, as well as the Balearic Islands, with a smaller number of reports from the Canary Islands.

Tabanidae family

A total of ten genera within the Tabanidae family were studied. Figure 3 shows the occurrence for four of the genera: *Dasyrhamphis*, *Philipomyia*, *Silvius* and *Nemorius*. The *Dasyrhamphis* genus was found mainly in central, southern and north-western mainland Spain, whereas the *Philipomyia* genus was predominantly observed in north-eastern mainland Spain. The *Silvius* genus was limited to a few sightings in northern and

southern mainland Spain. Finally, no specific coordinates were available for *Nemorius* genus; however, its presence was reported in central and northern mainland Spain.

The sightings of the *Pangonius*, *Haematopota* and *Hybomitra* genera are shown in Fig. 4. For *Pangonius*, sightings are distributed in the central, southern and north-eastern regions of mainland Spain. For *Haematopota* and *Hybomitra*, sightings were recorded both in mainland Spain (especially in the north and centre) and in the Balearic Islands.

Finally, Fig. 5 shows records for the *Atylotus*, *Chrysops* and *Tabanus* genera. The genus *Atylotus* was mostly observed in northern mainland Spain, though unspecified records exist for the Balearic Islands. The genus *Chrysops* was mostly restricted to central and northern mainland Spain. The genus *Tabanus* was reported throughout Spain, including the Canary and Balearic Islands, with notable concentrations in the north-east and central mainland.

Fig. 2 Geographic distribution of Muscidae family in Spain (1951–2024). The map shows mainland Spain (centre), the Balearic Islands (right) and the Canary Islands (bottom left)

Fig. 3 Geographic distribution of the genera *Dasyrhamphis*, *Philipomyia*, *Silvius* and *Nemorius* in Spain (1951–2024). The map includes mainland Spain (centre) and the Balearic Islands (right)

Discussion

This study, developed within the framework of the COMBAT project [8], represents the first comprehensive compilation of information on the potential vectors of Surra in Spain. Previous national atlases on trypanosome control and its vectors in African countries typically included both a tsetse component and an animal infection component [1, 21, 42, 65, 71]; however, this study focused exclusively on the entomological component, specifically on the three different dipteran families that can potentially transmit Surra in Spain. The Surra atlas for Spain has already been published [57], and to date, no vectors belonging to the *Glossina* genus have been reported in the country.

A notable gap in the literature relating vector presence to Surra in Spain became evident during the compilation of information sources. The present data reveal a high diversity of horsefly genera in the country, particularly in mainland Spain. Among these, the *Tabanus* genus stands out for its species richness and high abundance, and is the only genus found across mainland Spain, the Balearic Islands and the Canary Islands. Likewise, the *Hippobosca* genus (especially *Hippobosca equina* Linnaeus,

1758), *Melophagus* genus (*Melophagus ovinus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) and *Stomoxys* genus (*Stomoxys calcitrans* (Linnaeus, 1758)) are generally distributed throughout Spain. Among these, *S. calcitrans* is particularly abundant and found in diverse biotopes and environmental conditions. However, while the literature describes the distribution of *M. ovinus* as widespread, there is a notable lack of georeferenced sightings. It is also worth noting that only one record exists for the genus *Haematobia* (*Haematobia titilans* (Bezzi, 1907)) in the Canary Islands, with no subsequent observations to date.

Given the wide distribution of all the genera recorded in this study, potential re-emergent Surra outbreaks in Spain would likely encounter an abundance of competent mechanical vectors, as seen in past episodes in the Canary Islands and Alicante [82, 83]. In such scenarios, Surra could not only spread across Spain, but also pose a threat to continental Europe, as demonstrated by the 2008 outbreak in Aveyron (France), linked to the transport of infected dromedaries from the Canary Islands [15].

In addition to their potential role Surra transmission, bites from certain haematophagous flies pose an

Fig. 4 Geographic distribution of the genera *Pangonius*, *Haematopota* and *Hybomitra* in Spain (1951–2024). The map includes mainland Spain (centre) and the Balearic Islands (right)

occupational hazard and a considerable nuisance in rural areas of Europe [47, 54]. The study of these brachycerans flies in Spain has been far less extensive than that of nematoceran vectors, such as mosquitoes, sandflies and biting midges [9, 29] owing to their limited public health impact in urban settings and the lack of standardised trapping methods [77]. Another key factor is that these brachycerans rely on less refined capture methods than nematocerans do [48, 78, 85]. This methodology gap warrants further exploration to enhance our understanding of these vectors [2, 58]. For example, it would be necessary to standardise and optimise trapping methods for each of the families, especially in the case of louse flies, which generally require direct host contact for capture. In this context, carbon dioxide traps have recently proven effective for monitoring *Lipoptena* species in Spain [44]. For tabanids, comparative studies are underway to evaluate existing trap types and explore modifications for enhanced performance [48], also serving as mechanical control strategies. In North America, horseflies are often sampled using large open-style traps equipped with shiny black spherical targets, such as Malaise, Canopy, Box, Greenhead, Manitoba and Epps traps [7]. In Spain,

tabanids were successfully collected using custom-made Canopy traps, sweep nets and Malaise traps [43].

Notably, the genera included in this atlas do not reflect the full diversity of haematophagous flies in Spain. Furthermore, the absence of data from certain regions does not necessarily imply species absence. For example, within other blood-feeding Hippoboscidae within the Ornithomyiinae subfamily, primarily parasitised birds, are not included here owing to their limited relevance for Surra transmission.

This review highlights that some genera could act as potential vectors not only for Surra, but for a broad range of other diseases. For instance, the *Stomoxys* genus, and other muscids have been implicated in the transmission of salmonellosis, shigellosis, bacillary dysentery and even aspergillosis [5]. *Stomoxys* species are considered potential vectors of anthrax, a role they share with horseflies such as *Chrysops* spp. and *Tabanus* spp., both of which have been associated with tularemia transmission [6, 86]. Other studies highlight the role of the *Stomoxys* in the mechanical transmission of viruses (e.g., equine infectious anaemia virus, African swine fever virus, West Nile virus or Rift Valley virus), protozoa (*Besnoitia besnoiti*;

Fig. 5 Geographic distribution of the genera *Atylotus*, *Chrysops* and *Tabanus* in Spain (1951–2024). The map includes mainland Spain (centre), the Balearic Islands (right) and the Canary Islands (bottom left)

Besnoit and Robin, 1912) and helminths (*Habronema microstoma*; Schneider, 1866) [5], facilitated by their frequent and persistent feeding behaviour [22]. Similarly, Hippoboscidae (*Hippobosca*, *Melophagus* and *Lipoptena*), have been linked to viruses (e.g., border disease virus or bluetongue virus) and bacteria (*Rickettsia* spp., *Borrelia* spp., *Bartonella* spp. or *Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis*) [23].

The distribution maps presented in this study are subject to several limitations. They are based on local studies and citizen science data, with heterogeneous sampling efforts and methodologies. This reliance introduces potential biases and may not reflect current distributions or ecological dynamics. In addition, while citizen science data are valuable, they are not always consistent in terms of quality and geographic coverage. These issues underscore the urgent need for standardised, large-scale field surveys to produce more robust and updated distribution data. New surveys at the meso- and microscales could provide crucial insights into species ecology and interactions with potential hosts. Citizen science platforms

offer significant potential for this purpose, especially those with strong expert participation and photographic validation, as demonstrated by apps already implemented in Spain [45, 62]. Advances in artificial intelligence for insects recognition also offer exciting prospects for integrating automated data processing, whether by scientists or citizens [26, 50, 70]. Ultimately, cooperation between researchers, citizens, public health authorities and stakeholders could foster a more holistic and integrated vector surveillance and control programs in Spain and beyond.

Conclusions

This work represents a valuable contribution to the understanding of the epidemiology of *T. evansi* in Spain, as it is the first to consolidate and integrate information on the presence of its potential dipteran vectors across the country. Documenting the occurrence of these vector enables health authorities to implement more effective control and prevention strategies, as well as to respond promptly in the event of new outbreaks. Despite the findings presented, additional studies are

needed to further characterise the distribution of these vectors throughout the territory. In addition, the integration of citizen science platforms as a complementary tool for scientific research, significantly enhancing our understanding and surveillance of vector populations in Spain.

Abbreviations

COMBAT	CControlling and progressively minimizing the burden of animal trypanosomosis
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-025-06922-9>.

Additional file 1.

Additional file 2.

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Author contributions

Conceptualisation: M.T.T.J., J.A.C. and G.C.; Data curation: A.M.H., M.T.T.J.; Formal analysis: A.M.H.; Funding acquisition: M.T.T.J., J.A.C. and G.C.; Investigation: A.M.H., M.T.T.J., D.B.B., P.M.A.E., C.B., M.A.G., I.R.A.; Methodology: M.P., G.C.; Project Administration: M.T.T.J.; Resources: M.T.T.J., J.A.C.; Supervision: M.T.T.J., G.C.; Validation: M.T.T.J., J.A.C., G.C.; Visualisation: A.M.H., M.T.T.J., G.C.; Writing (original draft): A.M.H., M.T.T.J., D.B.B.; Writing (review and editing): A.M.H., M.T.T.J., D.B.B., P.M.A.E., C.B., M.A.G., I.R.A., G.C., J.A.C.

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Data availability

Data supporting the main conclusions of this study are included in the manuscript.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

- Ahmed SK, Rahman AH, Hassan MA, Salih SE, Paone M, Cecchi G. An atlas of tsetse and bovine trypanosomosis in Sudan. *Parasit Vectors*. 2016;9:194.
- Amarathunga DC, Grundy J, Parry H, Dorin A. Methods of insect image capture and classification: a systematic literature review. *Smart Agric Technol*. 2021;1:100023.
- Amisigo CM, Amegatcher G, Sunter JD, Gwira T. Adipose and skin distribution of African trypanosomes in natural animal infections. *Parasit Vectors*. 2024;17:215.
- Aregawi WG, Agga GE, Abdi RD, Büscher P. Systematic review and meta-analysis on the global distribution, host range, and prevalence of *Trypanosoma evansi*. *Parasit Vectors*. 2019;12:67.
- Baldacchino F, Muenworn V, Desquesnes M, Desoli F, Charoenviriyaphap T, Duvallet G. Transmission of pathogens by *Stomoxys* flies (Diptera, Muscidae): a review. *Parasite*. 2013;20:26.
- Baldacchino F, Desquesnes M, Mihok S, Foil LD, Duvallet G, Jittapalpong S. Tabanids: neglected subjects of research, but important vectors of disease agents. *Infect Genet Evol*. 2014;28:596–615.
- Baldacchino F, Desquesnes M, Duvallet G, Lysyk T, Mihok S. Veterinary importance and integrated management of Brachycera flies in dairy farms. In: Garros C, Bouyer J, Takken W, Smallegange RC, editors. *Pests and vector-borne diseases in the livestock industry*. Wageningen: Wageningen Academic Publishers; 2018. p. 55–90.
- Boulangé A, Lejon V, Berthier D, Thévenon S, Gimonneau G, Desquesnes M, et al. The COMBAT project: controlling and progressively minimizing the burden of vector-borne animal trypanosomosis in Africa. *Open Res Eur*. 2022;2:67. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=The+COMBAT+project%3A+controlling+and+progressively+minimizing+the+burden+of+vector-borne+animal+trypanosomosis+in+Africa&btnG=.
- Bravo-Barriga D, Ruiz-Arrondo I, Peña R, Lucientes J, Delacour-Estrella S. Phlebotomine sand flies (Diptera, Psychodidae) from Spain: an updated checklist and extended distributions. *ZooKeys*. 2022;1106:81–99.
- Büscher P, Cecchi G, Jamonneau V, Priotto G. Human African trypanosomiasis. *Lancet*. 2017;390:2397–409.
- Cecchi G, Paone M, Feldmann U, Vreysen MJ, Diall O, Mattioli RC. Assembling a geospatial database of tsetse-transmitted animal trypanosomosis for Africa. *Parasit Vectors*. 2014;7:39.
- Cecchi G, Paone M, Herrero R, Vreysen MJB, Mattioli RC. Developing a continental atlas of the distribution and trypanosomal infection of tsetse flies (*Glossina* species). *Parasit Vectors*. 2015;8:284.
- Cecchi G, Paone M, de Gier J, Zhao W. The continental atlas of the distribution of tsetse flies in Africa. PAAT Technical and Scientific Series, No. 12. Rome: FAO. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd2022en>. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=The+continental+atlas+of+the+distribution+of+tsetse+flies+in+Africa&btnG=
- de Gier J, Cecchi G, Paone M, Dede P, Zhao W. The continental atlas of tsetse and African animal trypanosomosis in Nigeria. *Acta Trop*. 2020;204:105328.
- Desquesnes M, Bossard G, Patrel D, Herder S, Patout O, Lepetitcolin E, et al. First outbreak of *Trypanosoma evansi* in camels in metropolitan France. *Vet Rec*. 2008;162:750–2.
- Desquesnes M, Biteau-Coroller F, Bouyer J, Dia ML, Foil L. Development of a mathematical model for mechanical transmission of trypanosomes and other pathogens of cattle transmitted by tabanids. *Int J Parasitol*. 2009;39:333–46.
- Desquesnes M, Holzmüller P, Lai DH, Dargantes A, Lun ZR, Jittapalpong S. *Trypanosoma evansi* and Surra: a review and perspectives on origin, history, distribution, taxonomy, morphology, hosts, and pathogenic effects. *BioMed Res Int*. 2013;2013:194176.

18. Desquesnes M, Dargantes A, Lai DH, Lun ZR, Holzmüller P, Jittapalpong S. *Trypanosoma evansi* and Surra: a review and perspectives on transmission, epidemiology and control, impact, and zoonotic aspects. *BioMed Res Int*. 2013;2013:321237.
19. Desquesnes M, Gonzatti M, Sazmand A, Thévenon S, Bossard G, Boulangé A, et al. A review on the diagnosis of animal trypanosomoses. *Parasit Vectors*. 2022;15:64.
20. Desquesnes M, Sazmand A, Gonzatti M, Boulangé A, Bossard G, Thévenon S, et al. Diagnosis of animal trypanosomoses: proper use of current tools and future prospects. *Parasit Vectors*. 2022;15:235.
21. Diarra B, Diarra M, Diall O, Bass B, Sanogo Y, Coulibaly E, et al. A national atlas of tsetse and African animal trypanosomosis in Mali. *Parasit Vectors*. 2019;12:466. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=A+national+atlas+of+tsetse+and+African+animal+trypanosomosis+in+Mali&btnG=.
22. Doyle MS, Swope BN, Hogsette JA, Burkhalter KL, Savage HM, Nasci RS. Vector competence of the stable fly (Diptera: Muscidae) for West Nile Virus. *J Med Entomol*. 2011;48:656–68.
23. Espinoza MA, Em D, Shahi-Barogh B, Berer D, Duscher G, Vloedt L, et al. Molecular pathogen screening of louse flies (Diptera: Hippoboscidae) from domestic and wild ruminants in Austria. *Parasit Vectors*. 2023;16:179.
24. Fetene E, Leta S, Regassa F, Büscher P. Global distribution, host range and prevalence of *Trypanosoma vivax*: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Parasit Vectors*. 2021;14:80.
25. Fraga J, Fernández-Calienes A, Montalvo AM, Maes I, Deborggraeve S, Büscher P, et al. Phylogenetic analysis of the *Trypanosoma* genus based on the heat-shock protein 70 gene. *Infect Genet Evol*. 2016;43:165–72.
26. Gao Y, Xue X, Qin G, Li K, Liu J, Zhang Y, et al. Application of machine learning in automatic image identification of insects—a review. *Ecol Inform*. 2024;80:102539.
27. García HA, Blanco PA, Rodríguez AC, Rodrigues CMF, Takata CSA, Campaner M, et al. Pan-American *Trypanosoma* (*Megatrypanum*) *trinaperronei* n. sp. in the white-tailed deer *Odocoileus virginianus* Zimmermann and its deer ked *Lipoptena mazamae* Rondani, 187: morphological, developmental and phylogeographical characterisation. *Parasit Vectors*. 2020;13:308.
28. García K, Martínez-López B, Cecchi G, Scoglio C, Matovu E, Muhanguzi D. Prevalence of African animal trypanosomiasis among livestock and domestic animals in Uganda: a systematic review and meta-regression analysis from 1980 to 2022. *Sci Rep*. 2023;13:20337.
29. Garrido M, Veiga J, Garrigós M, Morales-Yuste M, Recuero-Gil J. *Aedes albopictus* in a recently invaded area in Spain: effects of trap type, locality, and season on mosquito captures. *Sci Rep*. 2024;14:2131.
30. Gaston KJ. The magnitude of global insect species richness. *Conserv Biol*. 1991;5:283–96.
31. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.x35vrx>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
32. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.5ng5eh>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
33. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.ajvenn>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
34. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.2ad2ty>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
35. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.bx8bcq>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
36. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.vxgqj4>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
37. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.686jpb>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
38. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.u7fvem>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
39. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.bcusew>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
40. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.27h59s>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
41. GBIF.org. GBIF Home Page. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.bnjuke>. Accessed 6 Feb 2025.
42. Gebre T, Kapitano B, Beyene D, Alemu D, Beshir A, Worku Z, et al. The national atlas of tsetse flies and African animal trypanosomosis in Ethiopia. *Parasit Vectors*. 2022;15:491.
43. González MA, Stokes JE, Bravo-Barriga D. Diversity and abundance of tabanids in Northern Spain. *Parasitol Res*. 2022;121:87–96.
44. González MA, Ruiz-Arrondo I, Magallanes S, Oboña J, Ruiz-López M, Figuerola J. Molecular and morphological analysis revealed a new *Lipoptena* species (Diptera: Hippoboscidae) in southern Spain harbouring *Coxiella burnetii* and bacterial endosymbionts. *Vet Parasitol*. 2024;332:110300.
45. González MA, López-de-Felipe M, Magallanes S, Alarcón-Elbal PM, Barceló C, Martínez-Barciela Y, et al. Distribution, identification and ecology of *Phortica* genus (Diptera: Drosophilidae) in Spain. *Int J Vet Sci*. 2025;13:1–11.
46. Gutiérrez C, Montoya-Alonso JA, Padrón M, Corbera JA, Juste MC. Descripción de un caso de Tripanosomosis en el Dromedario por *T. evansi* En Canarias. *Med Vet*. 1998;15:356–7.
47. Härkönen S, Laine M, Vornanen M, Reunala T. Deer ked (*Lipoptena cervi*) dermatitis in humans—An increasing nuisance in Finland. *Alces*. 2009;45:73–9.
48. Henneker V, Jones R, Skerratt LF, Fitzpatrick LA, Reid S, Bellis G. A comparison of trapping methods for Tabanidae (Diptera) in North Queensland, Australia. *Med Vet Entomol*. 2008;22:26–31.
49. Hwang WS, Weirauch C. Evolutionary history of assassin bugs (Insecta: Hemiptera: Reduviidae): insights from divergence dating and ancestral state reconstruction. *PLoS ONE*. 2012;7:e45523.
50. Kariyanna B, Sowjanya M. Unravelling the use of artificial intelligence in management of insect pests. *Smart Agric Technol*. 2024;8:100517.
51. Kaufe J, Ellis J, Stark D, Barratt J. The evolution of trypanosomatid taxonomy. *Parasit Vectors*. 2017;10:287.
52. Kennedy PG. Clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment of human African trypanosomiasis (sleeping sickness). *Lancet Neurol*. 2013;12:186–94.
53. Krčmar S, Radolić V, Lajoš P, Lukačević I. Efficiency of colored modified box traps for sampling of tabanids. *Parasite*. 2014;21:67.
54. Laukkanen A, Ruoppi P, Mäkinen-Kiljunen S. Deer ked-induced occupational allergic rhinoconjunctivitis. *Ann Allergy, Asthma Immunol*. 2005;94:604–8.
55. Lukeš J, Spejjer D, Ziková A, Alfonso JD, Hashimi H, Field MC. Trypanosomes as a magnifying glass for cell and molecular biology. *Trends Parasitol*. 2023;39:902–12.
56. Magri A, Galuppi R, Fioravanti M. Autochthonous *Trypanosoma* spp. in European mammals: a brief journey amongst the neglected trypanosomes. *Pathogens*. 2021;10:334.
57. Melián-Henríquez A, Tejedor-Junco MT, González-Martín M, Doreste MM, Martel SM, Paone M, et al. An atlas of Surra in Spain: a tool to support epidemiological investigations and disease control. *Animals*. 2024;14:243.
58. Mihok S, Carlson DA. New materials for improving catches of horseflies (Diptera: Tabanidae) in Nzi traps. *Med Vet Entomol*. 2021;35:580–94.
59. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG. Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *BMJ*. 2009;339:b2535–45.
60. Molina JM, Ruiz A, Juste MC, Corbera JA, Amador R, Gutiérrez C. Sero-prevalence of *Trypanosoma evansi* in dromedaries (*Camelus dromedarius*) from the Canary Islands (Spain) using an antibody Ab-ELISA. *Prev Vet Med*. 1999;47:53–9.
61. Moloney NM, Barylyuk K, Tromer E, Crook OM, Breckels LM, Lilley KS, et al. Mapping diversity in African trypanosomes using high resolution spatial proteomics. *Nat Commun*. 2023;14:4401.
62. Alert M, Escobar A, Južnič-Zonta Ž. Mosquito alert dataset. Version 1.15. CREAM—centre de recerca ecològica i aplicacions forestals. Occurr Dataset. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1547/t5a1os>.
63. Mullen GR, Durden LA, editors. Medical and veterinary entomology. 3rd ed. London: Academic Press; 2019.
64. Nartshuk EP, Matyukhin AV, Shokhrin VP. Parasitic louse flies (Diptera, Hippoboscidae) and their associations with bird hosts in the south of the Russian far east. *Entomol Rev*. 2022;102:367–76.
65. Ngari NN, Gamba DO, Olet PA, Zhao W, Paone M, Cecchi G. Developing a national atlas to support the progressive control of tsetse-transmitted animal trypanosomosis in Kenya. *Parasit Vectors*. 2020;13:286.
66. Ogolla KO, Chemuliti JK, Wamwiri FN, Auma JE, Kurgat RK, Wanjala KB, et al. Spatial-temporal variations in parasitological prevalence and host-related risk factors of camel trypanosomiasis and its vectors in North Eastern Kenya: a repeated cross-sectional study. *J Parasitol Res*. 2023;2023:7218073.

67. Okello I, Mafie E, Eastwood G, Nzalawahe J, Mboera LEG. African animal trypanosomiasis: a systematic review on prevalence, risk factors and drug resistance in Sub-Saharan Africa. *J Med Entomol*. 2022;59:1099–143.
68. Onyilagha C, Uzonna JE. Host immune responses and immune evasion strategies in African trypanosomiasis. *Front Immunol*. 2019;10:2738.
69. Otranto D, Wall R. *Veterinary parasitology*. 5th ed. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell; 2024.
70. Pataki BA, Garriga J, Eritja R, Palmer JRB, Bartumeus F, Csabai I. Deep learning identification for citizen science surveillance of tiger mosquitoes. *Sci Rep*. 2021;11:4718.
71. Percoma L, Rayaissé JB, Gimonneau G, Bengaly Z, Pooda SH, Pagabel-eguem S, et al. An atlas to support the progressive control of tsetse-transmitted animal trypanosomiasis in Burkina Faso. *Parasit Vectors*. 2022;15:72.
72. Ramírez-Iglesias JR, Eleizalde MC, Gómez-Piñeres E, Mendoza M. *Trypanosoma evansi*: a clinical, parasitological and immunological evaluation of trypanosomiasis using a chronic rabbit model. *Open Vet J*. 2012;2:78–82.
73. Rodríguez N, Tejedor-Junco MT, González-Martín M, Santana A, Gutiérrez C. Cross-sectional study on prevalence of *Trypanosoma evansi* infection in domestic ruminants in an endemic area of the Canary Islands (Spain). *Prev Vet Med*. 2012;105:144–8.
74. Rodríguez N, Tejedor-Junco MT, González-Martín M, Doreste F, Gutierrez C. *Trypanosoma evansi* assessment in equines: a study in one decade in an endemic area of the Canary Islands, Spain. *J Equine Vet Sci*. 2013;33:406–9.
75. Rodríguez NF, Tejedor-Junco MT, González-Martín M, Gutierrez C. *Stomoxys calcitrans* as possible vector of *Trypanosoma evansi* among camels in an affected area of the Canary Islands, Spain. *Rev Soc Bras Med Trop*. 2014;47:510–2.
76. Rojo M, Hernández M, Campos F, Santamaría T, Dias S, Casanueva P. The Iberian Peninsula is an Area of Infection by *Haemoproteus payevskiy* and *Haemoproteus nucleocondensus* for the white-throated dipper *Cinclus cinclus*. *Ardeola*. 2015;62:373–82.
77. Ruiz-Arrondo I, Alarcón-Elbal PM, Figueras L, Delacour-Estrella S, Muñoz A, Kotter H, et al. Expansión de los simúlidos (Diptera: Simuliidae) en España: un nuevo reto para la salud pública y la sanidad animal. *Boletín SEA*. 2014;54:193–200.
78. Sasaki H. Capturing tabanids by traps: development history, visual and olfactory attractants and future of tabanid trap. *Med Entomol Zool*. 2016;67:205–18.
79. Sazmand A, Desquesnes M, Otranto D. *Trypanosoma evansi*. *Trends in Parasitology*. 2022.
80. Shereni W, Neves L, Argilés R, Nyakupinda L, Cecchi G. An atlas of tsetse and animal African trypanosomiasis in Zimbabwe. *Parasit Vectors*. 2021;14:50.
81. Stork NE. How many species of insects and other terrestrial arthropods are there on Earth? *Ann Rev Entomol*. 2018;63:31–45.
82. Tamarit A, Gutierrez C, Arroyo R, Jimenez V, Zagalá G, Bosch I, et al. *Trypanosoma evansi* infection in mainland Spain. *Vet Parasitol*. 2010;167:74–6.
83. Tejedor-Junco MT, Melián A, Puerto PP, Ramos MD, González-Martín M, Doreste MM, et al. Surveillance and control of *Trypanosoma evansi* in the Canary Islands: a descriptive analysis. *Acta Trop*. 2023;246:106990.
84. Tolrá MC, Andersen H. Catálogo de los Díptera de España, Portugal y Andorra (Insecta). *Monografías SEA*, vol 8. 2002.
85. Tunnakundacha S, Desquesnes M, Masmeatathip R. Comparison of Vavoua, Malaise and Nzi traps with and without attractants for trapping of *Stomoxys* spp. (Diptera: Muscidae) and tabanids (Diptera: Tabanidae) on cattle farms. *J Agric Nat Resour*. 2017;51:319–23.
86. Turell MJ, Knudson GB. Mechanical transmission of *Bacillus anthracis* by stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) and mosquitoes (*Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes taeniorhynchus*). *Infect Immun*. 1987;55:1859–61.
87. Williams RE. *Veterinary entomology: livestock and companion animals*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis; 2009.

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